

ture with sp^3 hybridization is suggested to these complexes.

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Titrimetric Determination of Osmium(VIII) and Iridium(IV) with Iron(II)

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ALTHOUGH quite a few titrimetric methods are available for the determination of osmium(VIII) and iridium(IV) almost all of them suffer from one disadvantage or the other; while some of them are cumbersome others are not sufficiently accurate. We have now developed more satisfactory titrimetric methods for the determination of these ions using iron(II) as reductimetric reagent in phosphoric acid medium.

Experimental

Determination of osmium(VIII) :

The titrimetric methods reported so far for the determination of osmium are based mainly on the reduction of osmium(VIII) to lower oxidation states using suitable reductants like iodide¹, thiosulphate², hydrochloric acid¹, titanium(III)¹, chromium(II)^{1,2}, bismuth¹, hexacyanoferrate(II)³ and iron(II) in alkaline medium in presence of mannitol or triethanolamine⁴. We now propose an accurate titrimetric method for the

determination of osmium(VIII) using iron(II) as a reductimetric reagent in phosphoric acid medium.

Reagents : An approximately 0.0025M solution of osmium(VIII) in 0.5M sodium hydroxide was prepared from osmic acid (Johnson Matthey Chemicals Ltd., London) and its strength determined¹. An approximately 0.01M solution of iron(II) was prepared and standardised in the usual way. 0.1% aqueous solutions of methylene blue and thionine were used as indicators. E. Merck, GR, Syrupy phosphoric acid (85%) was employed throughout the study.

Procedure : Enough syrupy phosphoric acid was taken in a 150 ml beaker so that the overall concentration of phosphoric acid was at least 9M (60% v/v) towards the end-point and the beaker was kept in ice-cold water. When the acid in the beaker was cooled sufficiently, an aliquot of osmium(VIII) solution (2-10 ml) was transferred into the beaker followed by 3 drops of methylene blue or thionine indicator. The contents of the beaker were titrated with iron(II) in an atmosphere of carbon dioxide, stirring the solution using a magnetic stirrer. (Care should be taken to see that the temperature of the solution being titrated does not exceed 25° as otherwise volatilisation of osmium occurs to some extent.) The end point was indicated by the disappearance of the blue colour of the dye. An indicator correction of 0.1 ml of 0.01M iron(II) was found to be necessary.

The accuracy of this method (range 1-5 mg of osmium) was found to be $\pm 0.8\%$. When ten samples, each containing 2.38 mg of osmium, were analysed the average and standard deviations were found to be : 2.37 mg, 0.013 mg (thionine); 2.37 mg, 0.014 mg (methylene blue).

Determination of iridium(IV) :

Most of the existing titrimetric methods for the estimation of iridium are based either on the reduction of iridium(IV) to iridium(III) or on the oxidation of iridium(III) to iridium(IV), using suitable redox reagents. The reductimetric reagents used in the determination of iridium(IV) are iron(II)^{1,5}, titanium(III)¹, tin(II)⁶, copper(I)¹, iodide¹, hexacyanoferrate(II)^{1,7}, ascorbic acid¹ and hydroquinone¹. Permanganate¹ appears to be the only oxidimetric reagent used for the estimation of iridium(III). We now report a new titrimetric method for the determination of iridium(IV) with iron(II) in phosphoric acid medium using both potentiometric and visual end-point methods.

Reagents : An approximately 0.01M solution of iridium(IV) was prepared by dissolving the required amount of sodium hexachloroiridate(IV) (Johnson Matthey Chemicals Ltd., London) in 0.5M hydrochloric acid and standardised¹. Solid sodium hexachloroiridate(III) was prepared as suggested by Poulsen and Garner⁸. From this solid an approximately 0.01M aqueous solution of iridium(III) was prepared and standardised¹. 0.1% solution of the indicators were prepared as usual.

Procedures :

(a) *Potentiometric method* : To an aliquot volume (2-15 ml) of iridium(IV) solution taken in a 150 ml beaker, enough syrupy phosphoric acid was added such that the overall concentration of phosphoric acid towards the end point was at least 1.5M (10% v/v). The titration was carried out by adding iron(II) solution in portions from a micro-burette, stirring the solution using a magnetic stirrer and noting the potential after each addition of the reductant. Carbon dioxide atmosphere was maintained in the titration vessel throughout the course of the titration to prevent aerial oxidation of iridium(III)⁹. The break in potential at the end point corresponds to about 70-100 mV/0.04 ml of 0.01M iron(II).

b) *Visual indicator method* : To 2-10ml of iridium(IV) solution taken in a 150 ml beaker enough phosphoric acid was added so that the overall concentration of phosphoric acid at the end point was at least 9M (60% v/v). Three drops of methylene blue or thionine indicator was added and the solution was titrated with 0.01M iron(II) in carbon dioxide atmosphere, stirring the contents of the beaker using a magnetic stirrer. The end point was indicated by the disappearance of the blue colour of the dye. An indicator correction of 0.1ml of 0.01M iron(II) was found to be necessary. When N-phenylanthranilic acid was used as indicator the titration may be carried out at an overall phosphoric acid concentration of 7.5M (50% v/v) and no indicator correction need be applied.

Results and Discussion

The accuracy of the potentiometric method (range 5-30 mg of iridium) was found to be $\pm 0.4\%$ and that of the visual indicator method (range 4-20 mg of iridium) $\pm 0.5\%$. The precision of the potentiometric method was determined by titrating six samples of iridium(IV), each containing 15.38 mg of iridium and the average and standard deviation from the range method¹⁰ were found to be 15.40 mg and 0.044 mg respectively. The precision in the visual indicator method was determined by titrating ten samples, each containing 9.61 mg of iridium. The averages and standard deviations were found to be 9.62 mg, and 0.022 mg respectively in the case of methylene blue as well as thionine and 9.61 mg and 0.0 μ g in the case of N-phenylanthranilic acid.

The potentiometric titration of iridium(IV) with iron(II) is feasible even in sulphuric acid medium but, the break in potential at the end point is very small, being only 15-20 mV/0.04 ml of 0.01M iron(II). It was however, noticed that this break in potential at the inflexion point increases in the presence of phosphoric acid reaching a maximum value at an overall concentration of 1.5M onwards. This may be explained on the basis of the formal redox potentials of the two couples involved in phosphoric acid medium. The formal redox potential of iridium(IV) / iridium(III) couple in media of varying phosphoric acid concentration were determined adopting a method essentially similar to that described by Rao and Dikshitulu¹¹. The potentials

thus obtained along with those of the iron(III)/iron(II) couple¹² were shown graphically in Fig. 1. From the figure it may be seen that the potentials of both the systems decrease with increase in phosphoric acid concentration, but the decrease is much more steep in the case of iron(III) / iron(II) couple than in iridium(IV)/iridium(III) couple in 0-1.5M range. However, the potential difference between the two couples remains nearly the same at still higher phosphoric acid concentrations. The potential data thus neatly explain the increase in the potential jump with increase in phosphoric acid concentration upto 1.5M.

Fig. 1. Formal redox potentials of Ir(IV)/Ir(III) and Fe(III)/Fe(II) couples in a medium of varying phosphoric acid concentration.

Ir(IV)=Ir(III)=0.0005M ; Total volume=100 ml ; Temperature=31 + 0.1°.

The transition potentials of the indicators used in the determination of iridium (IV) with iron(II) were also determined and found to be, 540 \pm 5mV (N.H.E.) in the case of methylene blue (in 9M H₃PO₄) ; 578 \pm 5mV in the case of thionine (in 9M H₃PO₄) ; and 770 \pm 3mV in the case of N-phenylanthranilic acid (in 7.5M H₃PO₄).

Interferences : Palladium(II), ruthenium(III) do not interfere in the potentiometric method. However, the colour of ruthenium(III) interferes in the visual indicator methods. Platinum(IV), Platinum(II) and ruthenium(IV) interfere by getting reduced to lower oxidation states.

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Kinetics of the Enolization of Cyclohexanone and *m*-Methyl Cyclohexanone Catalysed by Amino Acids

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MHALA and Singh¹ have reported the kinetics of enolization of cyclopentanone catalysed by mineral acids. Recently Mhala, Singh and Bhadoria have published their results on enolization of the above cyclic ketone catalysed by amino acids. In continuation with the above findings we present the kinetic data on the enolization of cyclohexanone and *m*-methyl cyclohexanone catalysed by amino acids with a comparative view point.

Materials and method :

The amino acids used were of A. R. variety. Analytical grade inorganic and organic chemicals were

used throughout the investigations. The method employed for the rate measurement is exactly similar to that of the previous communications^{1,2}.

Results and Discussion

Kinetics of enolization of cyclohexanone and *m*-methyl cyclohexanone (0.01 *M*) has been investigated at varying concentrations of glycine and DL alanine and β alanine. The results (Table 1) confirm a first order dependence each in glycine, and D. L. alanine and β alanine.

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF VARIATION OF AMINO ACIDS

(Amino acid) <i>M</i>	$k_1 \times 10^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$		
	β -alanine	DL-alanine	Glycine
0.40	2.570 7.943 *	1.778 5.495 *	0.98 1.67 *
0.80	7.586 16.220 *	1.5012 6.607 *	2.79 2.95 *
1.20	16.980 12.390 *	13.180 9.772	7.60 3.95 *
1.60	34.670 28.180 *	23.990 15.140 *	13.79 8.93 *

*Rate coefficient of *m*-methyl cyclohexanone at 45°.

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF VARIATION OF *m*-METHYL CYCLOHEXANONE

S. No.	(Glycine) <i>M</i>	(Substrate) <i>M</i>	Temp. 45°	
			$k_1 \times 10^3 \text{ min}^{-1}$	$k_1/S \text{ litre mole}^{-1} \text{ min}^{-1}$
1.	0.4	0.010	1.67	0.160
2.	0.4	0.012	1.81	0.150
3.	0.4	0.014	2.10	0.150
4.	0.4	0.016	2.50	0.156

Table 2 depicts the pseudo first order rate constants in *m*-methyl cyclohexanone which have been calculated by log (a-x), time plots. The slopes of the plots between log k_1 and log (substrate) have been found to be approximately unity which establish a first order dependence with substrate.

The enolization studies (glycine 1.2 *M*; substrate 0.01 *M*) have been carried out in a temperature range of 30° and the Arrhenius parameters have been calculated. The values of energy of activation,